

Two decades of progress in over one hundred years of study: Present status of Odonata research in Colombia

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Abstract. This study documents the results of a bibliometric analysis of 135 indexed publications concerning Odonata research in Colombia. A database including publications since 1868 was built through reliable sources on the Web of Knowledge. The publications were classified by time frame, departments (geography), study categories, and origin. All other categories were sub-classified according to the origin of the researcher, except for geographical classification. Contingence tables were constructed and analysed with Pearson's chi-squared test in the following analysis: i) number of papers per time frame according to the origin of the researcher; ii) separated number of papers for foreign researchers, network or Colombian authors over time; iii) number of papers per subject in accordance with the origin of the researcher; and iv) national or international publication according to the origin of the researcher. The number of documents per period, department, subject, and international or national publication were analysed by using chi square. The results showed the number of publications highest in Cundinamarca, Antioquia, Magdalena, Meta, and Valle. Departments least studied have been Arauca, Cesar, Guajira, Nariño, and San Andrés. The largest number of publications was taxonomic (83.7%) and most studies (78.5%) were published in international journals. The greatest progress in Odonata research in Colombia has been achieved since 2010. Current and future Odonata research in the country should cover more territory and prioritise research to provide information in order to generate conservation strategies in severely threatened Colombian ecosystems.

Further key words. Bibliometrics, dragonfly, damselfly, Latin America

Introduction

Odonata research in Colombia began at the end of the 19th and beginning of the 20th century with Anton Heinrich Hermann Fassl, Jesse and Edward WILLIAMSON (1918a, 1918b, 1918c, 1919a, 1919b, 1920), and others who collected, recorded, and described species in departments such as Magdale-

na, Antioquia, and Cundinamarca. Later, with the presence of De La Salle Brotherhood in the country, NAVÁS (1935) and Brother Apolinar MARÍA (1938) recorded several species. Then Odonata work within the country went dormant for the next 40 years, until the publication of a check-list with 237 species (DOS SANTOS 1981) and taxonomic works by ARANGO & ROLDÁN (1983) and CRUZ (1986, 1987, 1988). This information prevailed for 30 years, placing Colombia as one of the South American countries with fewest Odonata records. The 21st century brought the reactivation of Odonata research in the country, and at the beginning of the second decade PÉREZ-GUTIÉRREZ & PALACINO-RODRÍGUEZ (2011) compiled a check-list with a much larger number of species (335) from literature review and material from several national collections.

In Colombia, Odonata research has been limited because of problems such as few Odonata specialists; a difficult economic and political situation that restricts access to several regions of the country where illegal armed groups cause places to be little visited or studied (PÉREZ-GUTIÉRREZ & PALACINO-RODRÍGUEZ 2011; REGALADO 2013); a slow and complex legal system that demands documents that hinder biodiversity research (FERNÁNDEZ 2011); minimal financial support (only 10 % of Odonata research in Colombia was funded for researchers by an institution between 2001 and 2015); and even the difficulty in obtaining acetone to preserve specimens. In Colombia, access to acetone is severely restricted as it is a substance used for the synthesis of illicit drugs such as heroin and cocaine (SGCAN 2013).

This study is an attempt to show the course of Odonata research in a megadiverse country that requires crucial conservation decisions, as it is the country with the largest number of endangered odonate species in the Tropical Andes (BOTA-SIERRA et al. 2016). Therefore, present knowledge of the Odonata fauna must be made clear to counter the mistaken impression that Odonata research is non-existent or in danger of disappearing in Colombia!

The present study documents the current status of Odonata research in Colombia by gathering information to quantify the relevant publications from the following perspectives: (i) temporal; (ii) geographic; (iii) subject; and (iv) origin of publication (national/international). With the exception of geography, the perspectives were analysed in relation to the origin of the researcher (foreign, network, Colombian).

Material and methods

Data matrix and Information classification

A compilation of indexed literature about the order Odonata in Colombia was conducted by searching in the Web of Knowledge database (i.e., Biological Abstracts, Scopus). From this a matrix with search records was built in Microsoft Excel[®]. The literature was allocated to periods of 25 years, but arbitrarily the first (1862–1925) and last period (2001–2016) are longer and shorter, respectively, than the intervening periods. Then, each document was reviewed to look for the department(s) in which the study was conducted. Documents without specific department localities were assigned to the category ‘not specific’. Similarly, each publication was assigned to one of the subject categories (biology, ecology, evolution, or taxonomy) and to the origin of publication (national or international). Categories except geographic were classified according to the origin of the researchers: foreign, Colombian or foreign, and Colombian networking.

Data analysis

Data analysis was executed using SPSS software v20. Data tables were transformed into contingency tables, and then Pearson’s chi-squared test was executed for them. Contingency tables were used for the following analyses: i) number of papers per time frame according to the origin of the researcher (foreign, network or Colombian); ii) number of papers separately for foreign researchers, network or Colombian authors according to the time frame; iii) number of papers by subject according to the origin of the researcher; and iv) national or international publication according to the origin of the researcher. The number of documents by period, department, subject, and national/international publication, without taking into account the origin of the researcher, was analysed by using a chi-squared test.

Results

The refined database included 135 studies concerning Odonata in Colombia published between 1868 and 2016 in 58 journals of eight publishers. The journals with the most publications were *Odonatologica* (24 papers), *International Journal of Odonatology* (21) and *Zootaxa* (9). The publications involved 36 foreign and 42 Colombian authors. In the case of foreign au-

Table 1. Number of published papers on Odonata in Colombia, by department.

Department	n	Department	n	Department	n
Amazonas	13	Chocó	13	Putumayo	11
Antioquia	32	Córdoba	3	Quindío	5
Arauca	1	Cundinamarca	35	Risaralda	3
Atlántico	10	Guainía	1	Santander	11
Bolívar	9	Guajira	1	Sucre	3
Boyacá	13	Guaviare	2	Tolima	15
Caldas	5	Huila	3	Valle del Cauca	23
Caquetá	7	Magdalena	31	Vaupés	2
Casanare	2	Meta	25	Vichada	2
Cauca	7	Nariño	2	not specific	18
Cesar	1	Norte de Santander	2		

thors, there were persons with fifteen publications (1 author), fourteen (1), eight (1), six (2), five (3), three (1), two (4), and one (23). For Colombian researchers, there were persons with fifteen publications (1 author), eight (1), seven (2), six (1), three (6), two (5), and one (26). Between 2001 and 2016, 21 species were described (3 Anisoptera, 18 Zygoptera) by national (13 species) and foreign researchers (8 species).

The number of published studies for each department varied widely, with bias ($p > 0.01$) toward the departments of Cundinamarca, Antioquia, Magdalena, Meta, and Valle, a high contrast with departments such as Arauca, Vaupés or Vichada, which are among the least studied departments in terms of Odonata fauna, because these departments have been the center of political conflicts that have restricted access to researchers (Table 1). Significant difference was found between the period ($p > 0.01$) and subject ($p > 0.01$) when they were analysed without regard to the origin of the researcher. No significant difference was found in other analyses. The greatest progress in Odonata research in Colombia has been since 2010, a large number of publications were related to aspects of taxonomy (83.7%), and studies have mostly been published in international journals (78.5%).

Although there was considerable variation in the number of publications per year, the period 2001–2016 registered an increase of between 400 and 1 000% in contrast with previous periods. Similarly, until 1982 odonato-

logical papers were exclusively published by foreign authors, but during 1976–2000 the first four publications by Colombian researchers appeared, increasing to 48 between 2001 and 2016 (Fig. 1). That coincided with the beginning of publications by networks, especially in cooperation with other Latin American researchers.

Discussion

The increase of the number of publications coincides with the global trend in the study of biodiversity since 1990 (LIU et al. 2011). This increase is presumably a result of a recent increase in Odonata specialists to currently a dozen in Colombia, some of them with university degrees. These researchers have acquired the experience to guide research that generates quality publications in indexed journals. Likewise, more students and researchers have been involved in studying odonates in Colombia through research groups in local universities, where students have been developing theses in some cases networking with other national and international researchers.

Figure 1. Number of publications concerning Odonata in Colombia, considering period of time, study subject and origin of the publication. □ F – Authors are foreign researchers; ■ NT – authors are foreign and Colombian researchers networking; ■ C – authors are Colombian researchers.

Likewise, disseminating information has been facilitated through published works and papers presented at many local and international meetings. Odonates have been turned into a 'striking' group of organisms in our country. Additionally, the help of international researchers Álex Córdoba-Aguilar, Jurg De Marmels, Rosser Garrison, Enrique González-Soriano, Rodolfo Novelo-Gutiérrez, Dennis Paulson, Natalia von Ellenrieder, and others, has been crucial and we owe a great debt of gratitude for the collaboration that has promoted Colombian odonatology in recent decades.

Current and future research on Odonata will increase as the number of researchers increases through research groups. Currently, Cundinamarca has at least five active research specialists in odonates, and Antioquia and Magdalena have two, respectively. The Colombian Odonatology Group (COG) and formal research groups that currently work on odonates should stimulate both students and professionals to investigate adults and larvae, as the latter especially have been neglected in Colombia.

Because the discovery rate of new species is low as compared to trends in other groups of organisms, much more work needs to be done with the odonate fauna of Colombia. Review of the material deposited in collections and systematic sampling in the field, including the 59 protected areas, are crucial tasks to expand national knowledge of the group. For example, a recent visit to one of the Orinoquia region localities with the most sampling, Villavicencio, resulted in five new Odonata country records during only ten hours of survey (FPR & C. Bota-Sierra unpubl.). If such results can be achieved in a city with a human population growth rate per decade of almost 50% (SECRETARÍA DE PLANEACIÓN 2013), the potential for new species and records in Colombian natural locations is very high. National and international financial resources should be invested to help increase inventories, species description rates, and research in other aspects of odonatology.

There is also an urgent need to prioritise the investigation of other subjects such as ecology and behaviour to accurately define the conservation status of all species, some of which may be wrongly categorized at present. This information is necessary to propose and prioritise other conservation areas, an important issue for Colombian biodiversity, because many localities are rapidly disappearing as a result of deforestation for agriculture (PAOLILLO et al. 2001), urbanization, hydrocarbon pollution (ARZUZA et al. 2008), and

pesticides used on legal and illegal crops (LYNCH & ARROYO 2009). In spite of the research and publications in the last two decades, the path to follow is still complex, an outstanding opportunity for enthusiastic odonatologists of a mega-diverse country that has recently been considered *terra incognita* for Odonata (PAULSON 2004).

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